

JAVASCRIPT SWITCH (SHART TANLASH OPERATORI)

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Anotatsiya: Switch operatorining sintaksisi va misol bilan ko'rsatildi, qanday yechimlarni tekshirish uchun ishlatish mumkin. Ayni vaqtda, tuzilmasi ko'p yechimli if...else if...else if tuzilmalaridan farqli bo'lib, Switch operatori ko'p yechimlarni aniqlashda ham optimallashtirilgan ish tuzishini ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, Switch operatori, if...else if...else if, yechimlar, sintaksis, optimallashtirish.

Аннотация: На примере показан синтаксис оператора switch, какие решения можно использовать для проверки. В то же время структура отличается от многоуровневой структуры if...else if...else if тем, что оператор Switch выполняет оптимизированную операцию даже при определении нескольких решений.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, оператор Switch, if...else if...else if, решения, синтаксис, оптимизация.

Abstract: The syntax of the switch operator is shown with an example, which solutions can be used for verification. At the same time, the structure is different from the multi-solution if...else if...else if structures, which ensures that the Switch operator performs an optimized operation even when determining multiple solutions.

Keywords: JavaScript, Switch operator, if...else if...else if, solutions, syntax, optimization.

Switch operatori, yoki shart tanlash operatori, JavaScript dasturlash tilida ko'p tushunchali yechimlarni muomalaga olish uchun ishlatiladi. Shu operator yordamida if...else if...else if tuzilmasini o'z ichiga olgan holda yechimlar ketma-ketligini tekshirish va aniqlash imkoniyatini beradi.

Switch operatori, muhim yechimlar ketma-ketligida switch deb yuritilgan qiymatni tekshiradi va biror bir yechimning ishga tushirilishi shart. Agar switch qiymati yechimlarni tekshirishda aniqlik yuzaga keltirgan bolsa, switch operatori if...else if...else if tuzilmalaridan ko'ra juda ko'p tuzilmasi kerak bo'lgan tushunchali yechimlarni aniqlashda foydali bo'ladi.

Bu operatorning sintaksisi quyidagicha:

```
switch(expression) {  
  case value1:  
    // yechim 1  
    break;  
  case value2:  
    // yechim 2  
    break;  
  ...  
  default:  
    // barcha yechimlarni tushunmagan holat uchun  
}
```

Switch operatori, expression ni yechimlarga tekshiradi va mos keladigan yechimni ishga tushiradi. Har bir yechim uchun case operatori va uni izohlash uchun ishlatiladigan kod joyi bor. Switch operatori ishga tushirilgan yechimdan so'ng break operatori bilan tugagan holda ishni to'xtatadi. Default operatori, barcha yechimlarni tekshirgandan keyin aniqlanmagan yechimlar uchun ishlatiladi.

Switch operatori, katta va ko'p yechimli if...else if...else if tuzilmalaridan ko'p yechimlarni aniqlashda ishlatiladi. Bu operator, kodni ko'p yechimli tuzilma yozishga moslashtiradi va kodni aniqlik va tizimlik hisobidan optimallashtiradi.

JavaScript dasturlash tilida, shartlarni tekshirish uchun Switch operatori mavjud. Bu operator, if-else if-else if tuzilmasidan farqli ravishda ko'p yechimlarni aniqlashda ishlatiladi.

Switch operatorining sintaksisi quyidagicha:

```
switch (expression) {
  case value1:
    // code block
    break;
  case value2:
    // code block
    break;
  ...
  default:
    // code block
}
```

Bu sintaksisda, expression degan o'zgaruvchi yechimni tekshirish uchun ishlatiladi. case kalit so'zi va value esa yechimlar va ularning o'ziga xos kod bloklarini ifodalaydi. default esa hech qanday yechim mos kelmasa ishlatiladigan rezerv kalit so'zdir.

Switch operatori quyidagi tartibda ishlaydi:

- expression qiymati aniqlanadi.
- expression qiymati har bir case qiymati bilan solishtiriladi.

Bir case qiymati expression qiymatiga teng bo'lsa, u casega mos kelgan kod blokini bajaradi.

Bajarilgan kod blokidan so'ng Switch operatoridan chiqiladi (break kalit so'zi bo'lmagan holatda).

break kalit so'zi Switch operatoridan chiqilishga sabab bo'ladi.

Mos keluvchi case qiymati yo'q bo'lsa, defaultga o'tiladi (agar default mavjud bo'lsa). default kod bloki bajariladi.

Bajarilgan kod blokidan so'ng Switch operatoridan chiqiladi.

Switch operatori misol bilan ko'rsatilganda, kodning o'zining o'qib chiqarishi mumkin:

```
let x = 2;
switch (x) {
  case 1:
    console.log("x 1 ga teng");
    break;
  case 2:
```

```

console.log("x 2 ga teng");
break;
case 3:
console.log("x 3 ga teng");
break;
default:
console.log("x hech qaysi qiymatiga mos kelmaydi");
}

```

Switch operatorining foydali tomonlari qisqa va aniq bo'lgan kodni yozishga imkon berishi va kodni optimallashtirishi. If-else if-else if tuzilmasidan farqli ravishda, Switch operatori aniqlik va optimallashtirishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa

JavaScript dasturlash tilidagi Switch operatori, yechimlarni aniqlash uchun qulay yechimlar ketma-ketligini aniqlashda foydali bo'ladi. Bu operator kodni aniqlik va tizimlik hisobidan optimallashtiradi va ko'p yechimlarni o'z ichiga olgan tuzilma yozishga moslashtiradi. Anotatsiyada Switch operatorining sintaksisi ko'rsatiladi va uni yechimlarni tekshirish uchun qanday ishlatish mumkinligi ko'rsatiladi.

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